

Trident™ Thermal Conductivity Application Highlight: Importance of Representative Data in EV Thermal Simulations

The following Application Highlight addresses the measurement of materials for thermal simulation modelling using the Modified Transient Plane Source (MTPS) and Transient Plane Source (TPS) methods.

Thermal simulation is commonly used in electric vehicle (EV) development to understand and predict how heat behaves within the vehicle's components and systems. It involves creating a virtual model of the EV system and using specialized software to simulate heat transfer, temperature distribution, and cooling effects. Thermal simulation helps engineers optimize the design of EVs by evaluating and improving battery thermal management, HVAC systems, and motor & power electronics cooling. One important factor in thermal simulation is thermal conductivity, which refers to how well a material can conduct heat. Understanding the thermal conductivity of different components helps engineers determine efficient cooling strategies and select appropriate materials to enhance heat dissipation and prevent overheating, ensuring optimal performance and safety of electric vehicles. ThermoAnalytics, Inc. (TAI) is a leading developer of thermal, fluid flow, and infrared modelling software. Their flagship software TAItherm is a thermal simulation software, that produces transient test results within hours, solving for all modes of heat transfer. In collaboration with C-Therm, TAItherm and Trident were used in the testing for two specific case studies involving the thermal mapping of electric vehicles. Specifically, the mapping of electric motors and a NREL Thermal Runaway Model.

Figure 1. Thermal modeling of an electric motor with different potting compounds¹.

¹ Image Source: C-Therm Webinar – Importance of Thermal Conductivity in xEV Thermal Management Modeling Presented with guest speaker Dr. Zachary Edel in Partnership with ThermoAnalytics

To increase the thermal conductivity of the potting compound there are many factors at play. One being the addition of conductive fillers in the polymer matrix. Using the MTPS (ASTM D7984) sensor available on the Trident system, users can obtain representative data for their simulations. The MTPS sensor can also be used for thermal mapping by taking measurements in specific regions of the material to quantify the consistency throughout a component related to filler distribution. By combining the data obtained from Trident with thermal simulation software such as TAItherm, a thorough understanding of the impact temperature buildup has on an electric motor can be obtained (Figure 1).

Importance of Anisotropy in EV Battery Packs

The second study examined a NREL Thermal Runaway Model used to describe heating from unwanted reactions at elevated temperatures. This is then used to evaluate the risk of cell-to-cell propagation failure and to evaluate runaway mitigation. A thermal run-away pack setup was modelled in TAItherm with a shell geometry, cold plate edge cooling, and carbon fiber heat spreaders. The model was evaluated twice with different heat spreader configurations, anisotropic and isotropic heat spreaders. Using C-Therm's Transient Plane Source (TPS) Flex available on Trident, the thermal conductivity for both models were measured. The anisotropic heat spreader had a lateral conductivity of 2.4 W/mK and a vertical conductivity of 0.9 W/mK. In this configuration most of the heat was dissipated laterally into the cold plates on the side of the model, resulting in only the first two cells running away, followed by a cooldown. Conversely, in the isotropic heat spreader model, the heat spreader had equal lateral and vertical conductivities of 1.2 W/mK. In this model heat was dissipated equally in all directions resulting in all the cells

experiencing thermal runaway (Figure 2). In this situation, using an anisotropic system can lead to higher battery performance, extended lifetime, and improved safety.

Anisotropic Heat Spreaders

- Lateral Conductivity: 2.4 W/m K
- Vertical Conductivity : 0.9 W/m K

First two cells runaway, followed by cooldown

Isotropic Heat Spreaders

- Lateral Conductivity: 1.2 W/m K
- Vertical Conductivity : 1.2 W/m K

All cells runaway

Figure 2. Thermal modeling of an anisotropic (top) and isotropic (bottom) barrier during thermal runaway².

Anisotropic material characterization requires some additional considerations with regards to method selection and test setup. Many traditional methods for thermal

² Image Source: C-Therm Webinar – Importance of Thermal Conductivity in xEV Thermal Management Modeling Presented with guest speaker Dr. Zachary Edel in Partnership with ThermoAnalytics

conductivity testing are only designed for isotropic materials, which can significantly hinder a user's ability to quantify materials used in these applications. The MTPS and TPS available on Trident provide a complimentary means of testing both types of materials, ensuring valid data is obtained for simulation input.

Figure 3. C-Therm Trident system with MTPS and TPS sensors.

To learn more about C-Therm's Trident™ thermal conductivity instrument, visit www.TridentThermalConductivity.com